

Voices and texts in Swedish mathematics teacher education

Anna Pansell, Stockholm University, ✉ anna.pansell@mnd.su.se

Veronica Jatko Kraft, Stockholm University

Instead of getting access to the diversity of perspectives in mathematics education, prospective mathematics teachers read secondary sources of research providing a local or skewed image of the field. It then becomes important to see what is assumed scholarly sufficient for inclusion as texts for prospective mathematics teachers. The literature from a mathematics teacher programme, in Sweden, was submitted to an analysis of authors' occupation and country of residence as well as what types of texts the prospective teachers read. Through these texts, the prospective teachers were invited to participate in a local practice-based intellectual conversation. Besides risking not engaging with the forefront of research, there is a risk that prospective teachers are not sufficiently invited to challenge the educational philosophies with which they are accustomed.

Introduction

Different voices participate in mathematics teacher education. Voices from teacher educators, researchers and teachers in the field. Authors who write the compulsory literature for prospective mathematics teachers are counted as intellectuals with authority to speak about mathematics teaching and learning (Alvunger & Wahlström, 2018). Sayed et al. (2017) studied mathematics teacher education in South African universities to see who these writers were and what intellectual debates the prospective teachers were invited to through their course literature. They found that the prospective teachers got limited access to the multiple understandings of Africa's complex educational discourses and they concluded that "there is a need to provide intellectual fora for different actors to come together and think deeply and regularly about the meanings and processes which saturate their worlds" (p. 86). Sayed et al. describe this as a process of expanding imaginations, which involves rethinking what counts as relevant scholarship. To expand imaginations is described as a process of decolonisation where voices from different countries and cultures are given authority as intellectuals, which by extension offers access to competing perspectives from the intellectual debate. Inspired by Sayed et al.'s work, the present study begins with an interest in what texts the prospective teachers read and who the authors of these texts are.

Please cite as: Pansell, A., & Jatko Kraft, V. (2021). Voices and texts in Swedish mathematics teacher education. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 2, pp. 728–736). Tredition.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5415842>

What it means to expand imaginations can, of course vary; it could be to get access to influences from other countries, for example insights in educational philosophies underlying materials or methods that we might import (Kaiser & Blömeke, 2013). Competing, or at least different, perspectives are more often found in research literature than in the specifically written course literature (Alvunger & Wahlström, 2018). In the present study, we study the course literature and its authors in one programme for Swedish mathematics teachers to identify the prospective teachers' opportunities to expand imaginations. In this, we study what counts as relevant scholarship for prospective teachers in Sweden and the opportunities they have for a diverse understanding of educational philosophies.

The intellectual arena for prospective mathematics teachers needs to be broader than the culture of which they are already a part. In a plea for more cultural awareness in research of mathematics education, Andrews (2016) shows how mathematics education is deeply rooted in the culture within which it is carried out. Culture is here understood as the "covert culture", the way of life of the people that shapes mathematics education in a specific context (Knipping, 2003). International large scale assessments call attention to successful countries, creating a search for cross-national pedagogic excellence when it could be more reasonable to search for understandings of cultural differences (Andrews, 2016). Different cultures bring different educational philosophies which grounds mathematics education, and these philosophies needs to be taken into account in order to understand teaching methods and materials from different contexts (Kaiser & Blömeke, 2013). In multicultural educational settings, teachers need to be able to recognise cultural conflicts in interactions with students and parents from other cultures (Bishop, 1994). On the other hand, mathematics education, being situated within a culture, could imply a need for more locally situated mathematics teacher education, similar to what Sayed et al. (2017) highlight when they ask for more African authors in African teacher education. From the perspective of the programme studied here, which enjoys the privilege of being a European mathematics teacher education in a European country, the need however differs from a country where education has been imposed by a colonising power, such as South Africa. In Sweden, there is rather a need for access to competing or diverse perspectives of mathematics education to challenge set ways of thinking.

It is essential that prospective, professional, mathematics teachers get access to an academic intellectual arena. Swedish mathematics teacher education is based on mostly secondary sources of reference where the content is presented from a given perspective, strongly normative, instead of being discussed from different perspectives, as it is in research publications – and more so for prospective primary teachers (Alvunger & Wahlström, 2018; Pansell & Jatko Kraft, forthcoming). Swedish prospective mathematics teachers are immersed in the ways of mathematics teaching rather than getting access to its theoretical grounds (Asami-Johansson et al., 2020). Theoretical perspectives of mathematics education are, in Sweden, not always visible (Österling, 2021), which implies a need for access to research literature and theoretical grounds for the ways of mathematics education. On the other hand, in all educational systems there is a process of didactic transposition where elements of knowledge are translated between institutions. In this process, sometimes the rationale of

the knowledge gets lost (Bosch & Gascòn, 2014). Yet even if prospective mathematics teachers need access to the content taught in teacher education, it is undesirable for all readings to be reconstructed normative texts. This would strengthen what Asami-Johansson et al. (2020) describe as “immersion in the ways of mathematics teaching” with little visibility of the theoretical underpinnings. As Alvunger and Wahlström (2018) also conclude, this would enhance the possibility for well-informed professional teachers with scientific grounds for their practices.

The present study aims to explore the writers and texts of Swedish mathematics teacher education. That is, the agents and products of the transposition in this particular case. In this, we search for the prospective teachers’ possibilities to expand their imaginations into other cultural settings as well as different levels of academia. This is why we asked the following questions: “Who are the authors in the mathematics education courses?” and “What types of texts do the prospective teachers read?”

Methodology

The process of transposition is a central idea of ATD (the anthropological theory of didactics) where educational practices centrally is seen as part of a culture, one or more academic contexts, an educational system and more, all called institutions (Bosch & Gascòn, 2014). The theoretical grounds for the present study are, consequently, found within ATD. A central idea in ATD is that academic knowledge transforms through these different institutions on its way to teachers and students; it undergoes what in ATD is called a didactic transposition (Chevallard, 2006). People who think about education, constituting the noosphere, rewrite, or transpose, scholarly knowledge so it will be accessible for students, in this study prospective teachers. In this study, the authors of course literature are taken to represent the agents of the noosphere. These agents author different types of texts which thereby privilege practices of and/or perspectives on mathematics teaching. These texts can be normative through presenting teaching methods as best practice, but they can also be reflective and critical, presenting different perspectives.

The compulsory course literature is a central part of higher education since it is specifically chosen to cover course contents. The teacher programme in the present study is for prospective teachers of grades 4-6. The prospective teachers take four 7.5 ECTS courses in mathematics education: Teaching and learning of (a) number sense and arithmetic, (b) geometry, (c) relationships and change; and a course in curriculum studies, assessment and grading. The data for the present study is the compulsory literature in all four courses in mathematics education. From books, only the chapters included in reading instructions were selected as data.

Inspired by Sayed et al. (2017) we made an overview of the literature listing year of publication, number of pages, authors’ names and affiliations. The literature generally being secondary sources drew our attention to the references in the course literature. To be able to say something about the primary sources behind the course literature, we generated a similar overview of all authors and texts in the reference lists in the course literature of the first course on number sense and arithmetic.

Source	Course a	Course b	Course c	Course b	References in course a
No of texts	50	37	39	21	868
No of authors	24	32	39	27	465

Table 1: Overview of included texts

The agents of the noosphere, the authors, were categorised by their occupation at the time of publication and their country of residence. Some authors' occupation was already known, others were found in short descriptions of the authors, in the texts. Finally, for some authors we had to search for the information on, for example, university webpages. This means that an author can be interpreted as a Swedish teacher educator even if s/he is now researcher, living in Germany. Authors in the course literature were in many cases familiar to us which made it possible to categorise them as both researchers and teacher educators. Authors in the primary sources were in many cases researchers who may be teacher educators as well, yet this was not always possible for us to determine. We chose to include only certain information, wherefore the number in the author categories may not be entirely accurate.

The products of the noosphere, the kinds of texts the prospective teachers read were divided into the categories: (i) Books, chapters or papers written specifically for (prospective) teachers; (ii) Curricular materials, including textbooks, lessons or teacher guides; (iii) Policy texts, for example, national curricula or other texts authored by some of the national agencies connected to the educational system; and (iv) Scientific publications, such as scientific journal papers and scientific book chapters.

Findings

The overview of texts made it possible to say different things about who the agents and products of the noosphere were. The texts were relatively new, 90% of the texts had publication dates between 2000 and 2019. For the references, 50% were published between 2000 and 2019. About two thirds of the authors were female in the course literature. In the references from the first course there were about 40% female authors. Only six texts were authored by an agency, for example the Agency of Education, in the references from the first course 18 texts were written by an agency. We will now focus on the authors' occupation and country of residence, and what types of texts they wrote.

The authors' occupation

There were authors who were teacher educators only. There were also authors who were teacher educators as well as researchers. There was consequently a need for a diagram showing overlapping categories, wherefore the results are displayed as Venn-diagrams. In Figure 1, the categories are displayed in a circle with overlapping fields when there was a documented overlap.

Figure 1: The authors' occupation, in percentage of total amount of authors the two selections respectively. Authors of course literature to the left (101 in total). Authors of references in the course literature to the right (464 in total). A number, not the size of overlap, represents authors with double occupations.

The authors of these mathematics teacher education course materials are mainly teacher educators. The majority of them were also researchers. The researchers most often wrote about their research or about something connected to their research. However, there were also examples when researchers wrote about something other than their research, this as the case in about one fourth of the texts. One example of this is when the author wrote about the same things after as before their PhD. Such examples give the impression that researchers sometimes write more in their role as teacher educator than as a researcher. Despite what the researchers wrote about, it is clear that the prototypical author in this teacher education programme was a researcher and to some extent a teacher educator.

The authors' country of residence

To show the course material authors' country of residence we have displayed the number of authors from a specific country on a schematic world map. As a comparison, we displayed the country of residence of authors of the publications referred to in the first course. Placing the authors on a world map gives an image of how different parts of the world that were represented in these texts and consequently how the prospective teachers were offered possibilities to expand their imagination into other cultures. To simplify this image the countries of residence have been grouped. European authors are presented in Swedish, Nordic and other European countries. African and Oceanian countries are grouped per continent. Asian countries are grouped in Russian, Middle East and other Asian countries. In North America, both Canadian authors and authors from USA are displayed.

Figure 2: The authors' country of residence displayed on the world map.¹ To the left, the country of residence of authors for all four courses are displayed. To the right, the country of residence of authors of the references of the first course are displayed.

There was a concentration of authors from Sweden along with some authors from the other Nordic countries. Other than that, there was some authors from USA and the Oceanic countries. Looking into the references from the first course, one third of the authors came from Sweden (142) and about as many comes from USA (154). The last third comes from the Nordic countries (32), Europe (37) and Oceania (46). Except from two texts in German and twelve texts in Norwegian, the texts are in Swedish or English, about half each. The number of authors from Asia and Africa are negligible. No authors came from South America in either sample. In this mathematics teacher education programme it is clear that intellectuals are European, North American or Oceanian. The prospective teachers got little opportunity to read and by extension expand their imagination into Asian, African or South American educational cultures or practices.

Types of texts

The texts were mainly publications for teachers. Some of them were books written specifically for mathematics teacher education; some of them papers written for teachers with a diverse content, short reports, research or even teachers describing successful lessons. The publications for teachers were more or less normative describing how mathematics teaching should be done. An example of this was statements about students having to understand before they learn a procedure. In Figure 3 we show by percentage how large a part of the total references were publications for teachers/teacher education, curricular materials, policy texts or scientific publications. We also showed what type of texts that was referred by the texts in the first course.

The prospective teachers read almost exclusively texts written specifically for teacher education or teachers in general. Scientific publications were only a few. The lighter staples do, however, show that the scientific publications were present in the publications for teachers even though almost as many references also were publications for teachers. It is clear that the prospective teachers read research through the voice of someone, most often a Swedish researcher. They read transposed versions of research, of which Swedish researchers wrote 48 out of 259.

¹ Image from OpenClipart-Vectors on Pixabay

Figure 3: Type of text. The dark staple show what type of texts the prospective teachers read (145 in total). The lighter staple show what type of texts that was referred in the first course (554 in total).

Discussion

We posed questions about who authored course literature in this specific mathematics teacher education programme in Sweden and what kind of texts they wrote. In short, the answer is that Swedish researchers and teacher educators write publications specifically written for teachers and teacher education where they, at least in the first course, refer to one third Swedish and one third North American together with some European and Oceanian authors, all of whom had written research publication and/or publications for teachers. The prospective teachers' access to research was indirect, through what the course literature referred to, and even then, 40% of these references were publications for teachers. The intellectuals of the noosphere of this teacher education were, for the most, researchers mostly from what Bishop (1994) would call Western countries. English speaking countries dominated, there were only a few references written in another language than English or Swedish and all references from the first course were written in European languages. The prospective mathematics teachers got little access to cultural influences from either Asia, Africa or South America.

The studied mathematics teacher education programme offers what Sayed et al. (2017) claim that South African prospective teachers need more of: access to their local context of mathematics education. That is, if you leave out Swedish minority groups such as Sámi and Roma people, who are not represented in the literature. Rather, our findings indicate that the Swedish prospective teachers in this programme primarily had access to research transposed to their local context; research done in the same context or in the USA. Even if we take into account the total number of publications of educational research produced in the USA compared to other countries², there is still an over-representation of American research.

² <https://www.scimagojr.com/countryrank.php?category=3304>

There are however, other countries than USA affecting Swedish teaching practices, for example countries from where many have migrated. Despite this, there are only a handful authors from African and Middle East countries and none from South American countries. Other countries having direct effect on Swedish teaching practices are countries with high scores in PISA assessments since curricular materials are imported from countries such as Singapore (Andrews, 2016). Production of educational research in both Africa and the Middle East are scarce compared to USA³. Even if it still does not compare to USA, Singapore does have a more flourishing educational research milieu, not the least in comparative studies (see also Kaiser & Blömeke, 2013). Japan is another example of a country productive in educational research yet invisible in our findings. A more diverse understanding of educational systems from different cultures should extend teachers' opportunities to view, and understand, imported curricular materials or claims from immigrant parents or students. Connecting back to Sayed et al.'s (2017) study where decolonising is foregrounded, there is a possibility to contribute to the decolonisation of mathematics education. As long as "Western" countries maintain Western mathematics education, we also maintain colonisation of the mind. Opening up to diverse views on mathematics education, we also enhance possibilities for prospective mathematics teachers to view their own educational system and its cultural underpinnings critically.

Our findings confirm Alvunger and Wahlström's (2018) claim that Swedish prospective teachers read secondary sources of reference. We also show that the sources of this secondary literature are only slightly more research publications than secondary resources. Prospective teachers thus read research through the eyes of Swedish researchers who are familiar with the culture and educational philosophies within which prospective teachers will work. If these researchers transposed research from different cultures it would enable the prospective teachers to expand their imaginations as well as relating both research and different educational philosophies to the traditions of the Swedish school. The problem was that the literature, written by Swedish researchers and teacher educators relied on texts, many with secondary sources of research also written by Swedish researchers. This way, the traditions and set ways of Swedish mathematics becomes established as truths. Using researchers as authors give the literature a status of being scientific. Given our finding that only half the sources are scientific publications, the literature gives an illusion of being scientific, when it is rather a merge between research and texts written for teachers, which Alvunger and Wahlström (2018) describe as normative texts. The prospective teachers are left with the challenge to recognise what is research and what is an opinion or a tradition.

Our findings show that the studied mathematics teacher education did not offer diverse perspectives of theoretical underpinnings nor diverse educational philosophies. We argue that a scientifically grounded education requires prospective teachers to be invited, not only to read, but also to interpret research. Such education would enhance prospective mathematics teachers to become well-informed professional teachers with scientifically

³ <https://www.scimagojr.com/countryrank.php?category=3304>

grounded teaching practices (Alvunger & Wahlström, 2018). However, our analysis only show who wrote the course literature and of what kinds of texts it consisted. A deeper analysis of how different theoretical underpinnings and educational perspectives are covered and contrasted in a teacher education would give a more nuanced understanding of what possibilities the prospective teachers are offered to expand their imaginations and challenge the set ways of teaching of their culture.

Acknowledgements

This paper reports on research conducted in the TRACE project ([tracing mathematics teacher education in practice](#)) with funding from the National Research Council, project 2017-03614.

References

- Alvunger, D., & Wahlström, N. (2018). Research-based teacher education? Exploring the meaning potentials of Swedish teacher education. *Teachers and Teaching*, 24, 332–349.
- Andrews, P. (2016). Understanding the cultural construction of school mathematics. In B. Larvor (Ed.), *Mathematical cultures: The London meetings 2012–2014* (pp. 9–23). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-28582-5_2
- Asami-Johansson, Y., Attorps, I., & Winsløw, C. (2020). Comparing mathematics education lessons for primary school teachers: Case studies from Japan, Finland and Sweden. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(5), 688–712. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1614688>
- Bishop, A. J. (1994). Cultural conflicts in mathematics education: Developing a research agenda. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 14(2), 15–18.
- Bosch, M., & Gascón, J. (2014). Introduction to the anthropological theory of the didactic (ATD). In A. Bikner-Ahsbahs & S. Prediger (Eds.), *Networking of theories as a research practice in mathematics education* (pp. 67–83). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05389-9_5
- Chevallard, Y. (2006). Steps towards a new epistemology in mathematics education. In M. Bosch (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 4th Conference of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 21–30). CERME 4.
- Kaiser, G., & Blömeke, S. (2013). Learning from the Eastern and the Western debate: The case of mathematics teacher education. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 45(1), 7–19. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11858-013-0490-x>
- Knipping, C. (2003). Learning from comparing: A review and reflection on qualitative oriented comparisons of teaching and learning mathematics in different countries. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 35(6), 282–293. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02656692>
- Österling, L. (2021). InVisible theory in pre-service mathematics teachers' practicum tasks. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2021.1897874>
- Pansell, A., & Jatko Kraft, V. (forthcoming). *Opportunities to learn from the literature in Swedish mathematics teacher education*.
- Sayed, Y., Motala, S., & Hoffman, N. (2017). Decolonising initial teacher education in South African universities: More than an event. *Journal of Education*, 2017(68), 59–91.